

ALKALINE PROTEASES: A REVIEW ON PRODUCTION OPTIMIZATION PARAMETERS AND THEIR PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES

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Introduction

Proteins the indispensable part of all living forms has been mastered by a molecule of its own kind enzyme "Protease" (catalytic protein scissor). The world market for enzymes is expected to record Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of approximately 7.8% during the forecast period of 2015–2020 and reach USD 6.30 Billion in terms of value (1). Proteases

Abstract

Proteolytic enzymes are available in the entire livelihood and facilitate in growth of cells along with cell differentiation. Proteases are the hydrolytic enzymes that act as biocatalysts for the degradation of proteins into smaller peptides and amino acids. Microorganisms are capable and provide economical source of alkaline protease enzymes that are able to generate a constant and reliable supply of desired products. Alkaline proteases comprise the major group of enzymes from bio-industrial point of view with large number of applications. They play a significant position in diverse biotechnological industries, viz. in leather, detergent, food & feed and pharmaceutical areas. This review draws attention on different sources of proteases with particular consideration on bacterial alkaline proteases. A variety of nutritional as well as environmental parameters influencing the production of alkaline proteases with a foremost view from *Bacillus* species in submerged fermentation conditions are discussed. The biochemical characterization such as purification aspects along with the physicochemical properties of alkaline proteases from several *Bacillus* species are also addressed in brief which could facilitate to recognize enzymes with higher stability and activity above extreme temperature and pH, in order that they can be exploited for industrial applications.

Key Words: Proteolytic enzymes, Alkaline Proteases, optimization and characterization, Industrial uses.

represent one of the three largest groups of industrial enzymes and account for about 60% of the total global enzyme market (2). The most basic classification for proteases is: Neutral, Acidic and Basic (Alkaline protease). According to the Enzyme Commission (EC) classification, proteases belong to third class (hydrolases), and sub-group four (which hydrolyse peptide bonds) (3). Thus, Microbial proteases (EC 3.4.21-24 and 99, peptidyl-peptide hydrolases) are

among the most important hydrolytic enzymes that hydrolyse proteins via the addition of water across peptide bonds (4). Four mechanistic classes are documented by the EC and in these classes; six families of proteases are recognized till date: serine proteases (EC 3.4.21), serine carboxy proteases (EC 3.4.16), cysteine proteases (EC 3.4.22), aspartic proteases (EC 3.4.23), metallo peotases I (EC 3.4.24) and metallo carboxy proteases (EC 3.4.17) (5). In contrast to plants and animals, microbes represent as a better source of proteases because they can be cultured in large volume in a short duration, are comparatively inexpensive, and can produce a continuous supply of metabolites. Being extracellular in nature and are directly secreted by the producer organism into the fermentation medium, simplified the downstream processing of the enzyme (6). The kind & volume of contribution made by researchers towards all the three type of proteases, it's difficult to summarize all in one article. Hence, the present study attempts to review alkaline proteases from microbes in general and *Bacillus* species in particular.

Among microorganisms, the genus "*Bacillus*" is an important source of industrial alkaline proteases and is probably the only genus being commercialized for alkaline protease production (7-8). The reason for this is their wide temperature, pH tolerance and thermal stability (9). The first alkaline protease Carlsberg (BIOTEX) from *B. licheniformis* was commercialized as an additive in detergents in the 1960s (10). *Bacillus* derived alkaline proteases are of immense utility in different sectors. The potent avenues that established with use of alkaline proteases are detergent, leather,

pharmaceuticals, food, textile, silk, bakery, soy processing, meat tendering, brewery, protein processing, peptide synthesis, ultra filtration membrane cleaning and recovery of silver from photographic films (11-13). Owing to their immense demand in industries, researchers are persistently investigating diverse aspects of proteases (14).

Laboratories engaged in alkaline protease production studies are making efforts to improve upon existing potential alkaline protease producing bacteria, particularly belonging to *Bacillus* sp. In this regard, different biotechnological approaches like immobilized cells, gene amplification etc. have been employed (8, 15-16). Therefore, keeping in view the importance of alkaline proteases in different sectors, the review will focus on potential emerging strains for alkaline protease along with production, purification and properties of alkaline proteases.

Potential Emerging Strains for Alkaline Protease

Emerging strains are need of the hour for the fulfillment of the high demand of alkaline protease in present scenario. Potential microbes has been screened, studied and established for extracellular alkaline protease production. Amongst microbes bacteria has been appraised for its potential to produce extracellular protease production. More than 50 species of *Bacillus* has been established for alkaline protease production. The percentage distribution of various microbes for alkaline protease production (Fig 1) are as follows bacteria, fungus and actinomycetes are 81, 11 and 8%, respectively.

Fig. 1 Percentage distribution of alkaline protease producing microorganisms

Bacteria

Bacterial strains have been the major source of alkaline proteases with the genus *Bacillus* being the most predominant source (Table 1). The most potential alkaline proteases producing bacilli are the strains of *B. licheniformis*, *B. subtilis*, *B. amyloliquefaciens*, *B. mojavensis* and *B. circulans* (17- 20). Microbial proteases, especially from *Bacillus* sp. have traditionally held the predominant share of the industrial enzyme market of the worldwide enzyme sales with major application in detergent formulations (21).

The first report about commercial use of an alkaline protease enzyme was that of an extracellular alkaline serine protease from alkalophilic *Bacillus* strain 221 during 1971. Bacterial alkaline proteases are in general characterized by their high activity at alkaline pH, for instance, pH 10 and their broad substrate specificity. Their optimal temperature is around 60°C. These properties of bacterial alkaline proteases make them suitable for use in the detergent industry.

Table 1. Different alkaline protease producing bacterial species

<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	Source (Reference)
<i>Oceanobacillus iheyensis</i> O.M.A18	(22)
<i>B. alcalophilus</i> ATCC 21522	(23)
<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	(19)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	(24)

<i>Bacillus</i> sp. SSR1	(25)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. MIG	(26)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. L21	(27)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. GPA4	(28)
<i>B. subtilis</i>	(29-30)
<i>B. subtilis</i> MTCC N0-10110	(31)
<i>B. subtilis</i> SVR-07	(32)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> RSKK96	(33)
<i>B. firmus</i>	(34)
<i>B. firmus</i> Tap5	(35)
<i>B. proteolyticus</i>	(36)
<i>B. thuringiensis</i>	(37)
<i>B. licheniformis</i>	(38)
<i>B. licheniformis</i> NCIM-2042	(39)
<i>B. pseudofirmus</i> AL-89	(40)
<i>B. circulans</i>	(20)
<i>B. cereus</i>	(41)
<i>B. cereus</i> VITSN04	(42)
<i>B. amovivoorus</i>	(43)
<i>B. proteolyticus</i> -CFR3001	(11)
<i>B. aquamoris</i>	(44)
<i>Bacillus clausii</i>	(45)
<i>Bacillus sphaericus</i>	(46)
Thermophilic strains	Source
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. JB-99	(47)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. Strain SMIA 2	(48)
<i>Bacillus</i> RV.B2.90	(49)
<i>B. licheniformis</i> RP1	(50)
<i>B. thermoruber</i> BT2T	(51)
<i>B. stearothermophilus</i> TLS33	(52)
<i>B. pumilus</i> CBS	(53)
<i>Thermomonospora fusca</i>	(54)
<i>Thermoactinomyces</i> sp.	(55)
<i>A. stearothermophilus</i>	(56)
<i>Geobacillus</i>	(57)

<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	(58)
<i>Vibrio fluvialis</i> strain VM10	(59)
Gamma-Proteobacterium	(60)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. Ve1	(24)
<i>Bacterium</i> O.M.E12	(22)

Fungi and Actinomycetes

Fungi present a wide variety of proteases than do the bacteria (Table 2). They are active over a wide range of pH eg., *Aspergillus oryzae* produces acidic, neutral and alkaline proteases which have broad substrate specificity but they have low reaction rate and lesser heat tolerance than bacterial proteases. Fungal alkaline proteases are used in food protein modification. Among fungi, *Aspergillus* sp. (61), *Conidiobolus* sp. and *Rhizopus* sp. (62) also produce alkaline proteases. Among yeast, *Candida* sp. has been studied in detail as a potent alkaline protease producer (63).

Among actinomycetes (Table 3), strains of *Streptomyces* are preferred protease sources (64). Partial purification and characterization of a novel alkaline protease produced by *Nocardia* sp. was reported by Moreira *et al* (65). The serine and metalloproteases produced by *Streptomyces* sp. 594 in submerged (SF) and solid-state fermentation (SSF), using feather meal, an industrial poultry residue (keratinous waste) and corn steep liquor (corn processing by-product), were found to be active over a wide range of pH (5.0-10.0) and high temperatures (55-90°C) (66).

Table 2 Alkaline protease producing fungal species

Fungi	Source Reference
<i>Penicillium charlesii</i>	(67)
<i>P. lilacinus</i>	(68)
<i>P. griseofulvum</i>	(69)
<i>Fusarium graminearum</i>	(70)
<i>Chrysosporium keratinophilum</i>	(71)
<i>Scedosporium apiosermum</i>	(72)
<i>A. melleus</i>	(73)
<i>A. niger</i>	(74)
<i>A. fumigatus</i>	(75)
<i>A. flavus</i>	(76)
<i>A. terreus</i>	(61)
<i>A. clavatus</i>	(77)
<i>A. nidulans</i> HA-10	(78)
<i>A. oryzae</i>	(79)
<i>A. awamori</i>	(80)
<i>Conidiobolus coronatus</i>	(81)
<i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	(82)

Table 3 Alkaline protease producing Actinomycetes

Actinomycetes	Source reference
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. CN902	(83)
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. DP2	(64)
<i>Streptomyces</i> NRRLB-8165	(84)
<i>Streptomyces fradial</i>	(85)
<i>Streptomyces penutius</i>	(86)
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. 594	(66)
<i>Streptomyces pseudogrisiolus</i> NCR-15	(87)
<i>Nocardioopsis Alkalophila</i> sp Nov.	(88)
<i>Nocardioopsis</i> TOA-1	(89)
<i>Nocardioopsis</i> sp. NCIM 5124	(90)
<i>Saccharomonospora viridis</i> SJ-21	(91)

Microbial Production of Alkaline Protease

Protease production is an inherent property of all organisms and these are generally constitutive however at times they are partially inducible (92). The proteases are largely produced during stationary phase and thus are generally regulated by carbon and nitrogen stress. Different methods in submerged fermentations have been used to regulate the protease synthesis by combinations of either of the strategies, such as fed-batch, continuous, and chemostat cultures (93). These strategies have resulted in high yields of alkaline protease in the fermentation medium (94).

Protease being associated with the onset of stationary phase, their production is often related to the sporulation stage in many bacilli, such as *B. subtilis* and *B. licheniformis* (95). On the contrary, few reports also suggest that sporulation and protease production though may co-occur, but are not related as the spore-deficient strains of *B. licheniformis* (96) and *B. stearothermophilus* (97) were not protease-deficient. A similar observation has also been reported in *B. licheniformis* by analysis of nucleotide pools (GTP and ATP) in the cells (98). These

results strongly suggested that the protease production is under stringent response to amino acid deficiency and is related to the Gppp ratio in the cell. The transitions between different growth phases or different nutritional limitations can be discerned by the alterations in the nucleotide pool as a marked decrease in the GTP content of the cells (after addition of mycophenolic acid in the exponential phase) was found to increase the protease production during the stationary phase (95).

Hence, it conclusively suggests that extracellular protease production is a manifestation of nutritional limitation, at the onset of stationary phase. However, final protease yield during this phase is also determined by the biomass produced during exponential phase. Therefore, media manipulations are needed to maximize growth and hence protease yields.

Effect of carbon sources on alkaline protease production

Carbon sources used in the culture media vary greatly in type and concentration for different types of bacteria and other microorganisms. Among various types of

carbon sources, carbohydrates are used predominantly. Majority of the microorganisms utilize glucose and starch as the preferred source of carbon, though other types of carbohydrate and non-carbohydrate sources have been reported to be utilized by protease producing microorganisms (51, 70). In different studies, glucose, glycerol, starch, sucrose, fructose, maltose, galactose and lactose have been reported as optimum carbon sources for alkaline protease production (92, 99). Mukherjee *et al* (100) used glucose, fructose, galactose, maltose, sucrose and lactose (10% w/w) for alkaline protease production by thermophilic *B. subtilis* with maltose supporting maximum alkaline protease production under solid state fermentation as co-carbon source. Lactose was reported as the best carbon source for protease production by *B. halodurans* with a specific activity of 135.5 U/mg protein, which indicated that, this bacterium was able to produce β -galactosidase for consuming lactose (101). Among other carbon sources, *B. alcalophilus* TCCC11004 exhibited highest productivity of alkaline protease in medium containing maltodextrin (102), *B. cereus* MTCC 6840 utilized fructose as preferred carbon source (157) while whey and sucrose were used preferably by *Serratia marcescens* ATCC 25419 (104).

Glucose, the most commonly used carbon source has been shown to be inhibitory for alkaline protease production in some bacteria such as *Geobacillus caldoproteolyticus* strain SF03 (105), *B. horikoshii* (106) and *B. nesternkonina* sp. AL-20 (40). This negative effect of glucose on protease production is attributed to catabolite repression as it has been established that the catabolite control protein (Ccp A) is responsible for the regulatory mechanism of glucose catabolism, and acts as a signal for the

repression in protease synthesis (107). On the other hand, in some *Bacillus* strains such as *Bacillus* sp. AR 009 (108), *B. licheniformis* ATCC 21415 (109), *B. thuringiensis* cc7 (110), *B. licheniformis* N-2 (111), *Bacillus* sp. EL31410 (112) and *B. cereus* strain 146 (113), enhanced protease yields have been reported upon supplementation of glucose in the production medium.

Besides glucose, starch is another widely used carbon source and has been shown to induce protease synthesis in alkalophilic *B. pumilus*, *B. cereus* MCM B-326 and *Bacillus* sp. 2-5 (114-116), but was found to be dependent on starch type. However, supplementation of potato starch, corn starch, and pearl millet flour exerted an inhibitory effect on alkaline protease production in *Bacillus* sp. Y (117). This negative influence on enzyme synthesis was probably due to the presence of protease inhibitors in these carbon sources (118).

Natural agricultural materials such as Rice bran, soybean, wheat flour, wheat bran, corn bran, corn starch, orange peels have been reported to produce alkaline proteases (119-120). Ahmed *et al* (121) also observed the effect of different carbon substrates i.e. sunflower meal, soybean meal, cotton seed meal, rice husk, rice polish, rice bran and wheat bran on alkaline protease production where by maximum activity was found on rice husk (110.42 U/ml). Furthermore, Kumar *et al* (122) observed wheat bran as the best carbon source with the maximum protease activity of 1160 U/ml. Molasses as a supplement was also found to be effective for protease production in *Bacillus* species (123, 124). In another report, wheat bran, rice bran and Cotton Deoiled Meal (CDM) was used in the production medium (125). The use of CDM revealed a maximum alkaline protease production (589.20 U/ml) with glucose as carbon source.

Non-carbohydrate sources such as organic acids as sole carbon sources have also been found to increase the yield of alkaline protease by *Bacillus* sp. B1 (126). Researchers studied the effect of citrate, fumarate, succinate, glucose and fructose on protease production by *B. alcalophilus* and found that citrate, fumarate and succinate can be effectively utilized for protease production with citrate at 1.0% level being the most potent carbon source (127). Calik *et al* (128) used citric acid as a sole carbon source for alkaline protease production by *B. licheniformis*. On the other hand, the presence of citric acid and trisodium citrate in the medium repressed the growth and yield of alkaline protease by *B. licheniformis* N-2 (111). The citric acid inhibition is attributed to chelation of divalent ions from the medium, resulting in ion depletion in the growth medium (129).

Effect of nitrogen sources on alkaline protease production

Synthesis of the alkaline protease by microorganisms is strongly stimulated by the presence of the nitrogen sources (proteins and peptides) in the culture medium, which have regulatory effects on enzyme synthesis (24). Different bacteria have diverse preferences for either organic or inorganic nitrogen for growth and protease production, although complex nitrogen sources are usually employed for alkaline protease production (100, 130).

Mukherjee *et al* (100) has shown a preference for organic nitrogen sources (beef extract followed by yeast extract) compared to inorganic nitrogen for protease production by *B. subtilis* DM-04. The inducing effect of nitrogen sources (peptone, soybean meal and beef extract) on bacterial alkaline protease production has also been reported by (131-132). A mixture of nitrogen sources

i.e. yeast extract in addition to casamino acid, peptone or L-glutamate were used and achieved highest protease activity was observed with *Bacillus* sp. 2-5 (116). In addition to this, a combination of yeast extract and cotton seed meal induced maximum alkaline protease production by *B. alcalophilus* TCCCC11004 (102). In a sharp contrast to these observations, organic nitrogen sources like peptone and yeast extract were found to suppress the protease production by an alkalophilic strain of *Arthrobacter ramosus* MCM B351 (133). However, Patel *et al* (24) observed higher protease production with organic nitrogen sources. Similarly, free amino acids and inorganic nitrogen sources, such as NH_4Cl , NH_4NO_3 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ have been reported to repress enzyme synthesis in *Bacillus* sp. (134, 116, 136). The repression of growth and protease biosynthesis is thought to be due to the fast release of ammonia from these inorganic nitrogen sources (111). Inorganic nitrogen sources such as ammonium nitrate (48), $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (110) have been successfully used as optimal nitrogen sources.

Skim milk exhibited a prominent effect on protease production by *B. subtilis* (121). Furthermore, *B. mojavensis* produced maximum alkaline protease when casein and casamino acids are used as nitrogen sources (94). The maximum protease production was exhibited with gelatin concentration at 1% (w/v) for *B. anthracis* S-44 and *Bacillus* sp. K 30 (137), 0.5 % (w/v) for *B. firmus* 7728 (138). Saurabh *et al* (139) observed maximum alkaline protease production in the presence of casein from *Bacillus* sp. and *B. pseudofirmus* SVB1, respectively. While, Kanekar *et al* (140) used soya-cake as the exclusive carbon and nitrogen source for protease production. Groundnut cake as the main nitrogen source gave maximum protease activity of 940

U/ml by *Bacillus* sp. (122). Kanchana and Padmavathy (141) observed Bengal gram powder as the best substrate for highest enzyme activity.

Among the natural complex substances employed as nitrogen sources, Corn Steep Liquor (CSL) was found to be a cheap and suitable source of nitrogen by some workers (142). Apart from serving as a nitrogen source, CSL also provides several micronutrients, vitamins, and growth-promoting factors. However, its use is limited by its seasonal and interbatch variability. While, Moreira *et al* (65) found that *B. pumilus* UN-31-C-42 showed maximum protease production on 2% bean powder preferably, when supplemented to the medium, *Bacillus* sp. JB-99 used KNO₃ as the preferred nitrogen source (47).

Now days, there has been increasing trend to utilize raw/unprocessed carbon and nitrogen sources so as to cut down the cost of production. Hence, there are many reports where agricultural or industrial by/waste products are being used for cultivation of microorganisms. Soybean contains 40% of protein, 17% carbohydrate, 18% oil, traces of metals, moderate amount

of vitamins and amino acids, thus supplying almost all the nutrients required for the growth of bacilli. Besides that, soybean also contains small amount of enzymes such as protease, urease and lipoxidase (139). Soybean meal has been used as inducer for protease production from *Conidiobolus coronatus* (143), *B. cereus* MCM B-326 (115), *B. licheniformis* N-2 (111), recombinant *B. subtilis* (144), *B. subtilis* BS1 (145) and *Bacillus* sp. I-312 (146). The protease production was considerably enhanced (4771 U/ml) when *B. licheniformis* NH1 was grown in medium containing hulled grain of wheat as nitrogen source (147). Chu (148) used a combination of wheat flour and soybean meal for optimized alkaline protease production (2560 Uml⁻¹) by *Bacillus* sp., rice bran @ 1 per cent (120), wheat bran and lentil husk (149), wheat bran @ 2.5 per cent (150) and combination of glucose and soybean meal (125) were also found suitable for production of alkaline protease in different studies.

A comprehensive account of cultural conditions for maximum alkaline protease production from various *Bacillus* sp. has been listed in **Table 4**.

Table 4: Fermentation conditions for production of alkaline proteases from bacteria

Microorganism	pH	Temperature (°C)	Agitation (rpm)	Incubation period (h)	Nitrogen sources	Carbon sources	Reference
<i>Bacillusmycoides</i>	7	30	180	48	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ , peptone	Glycerol	(151)
<i>Bacillus polymyxa</i>	9	50	n.s.	72	Casein	Glucose	(132)
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> ATCC 21415	7	30	250-400	48	Soybean, (NH ₄) ₂ PO ₃	Lactose, Glucose	(109)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	8	37	120	18	Peptone, yeast extract	Glucose	(152)
<i>B. horikoshii</i>	9	34	250	16-18	Soybean, casein	*	(106)
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i> MK6-5	9.6	35	250	60	Corn-steep liquor	Glucose	(153)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> PE-11	9	37	140	48	Peptone	Glucose	(154)
<i>B. mojavensis</i>	10.5	50	250	10-12	Casamino acid	Glucose	(155)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. RGR-14	7	37	250	96	Soybean meal, casamino acid	Starch	(156)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp. MIG	7.5	30	120	48	Yeast extract	Wheat bran	(26)
<i>B. cereus</i> MTCC 6840	9	25	150	24	Yeast extract + Peptone	Fructose	(157)
<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	9	50	n.s.	48	Soybean meal	Wheat flour	(148)
<i>B. cereus</i> MCM B-326	9	30	100	36	Soybean meal	Starch	(115)
<i>B. circulans</i>	10.5	25-30	200	96	Soybean meal	Glucose	(125)
<i>B. licheniformis</i> RPK	9	37	200	48	Yeast extract	Chicken fearhers	(136)
<i>B. alcalophilus</i> TCCC11004	9	34	180	50	Yeast extract, cotton seed meal	Glucose, maltodextrin	(102)
<i>B. thuringiensis</i> cc7	8.5	29	150	48	Casein, urea,	Glucose	(110)
<i>B. licheniformis</i> NCIM-2042	7.1	37	180	86	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	Starch	(39)
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp. DP2	5	50-100	250	72-96	Soybean meal	fructose	(158)
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> ATCC 12759.	7	37	-	-	Mustard cake	Wheat flour	(159)
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> P003	9.0	25	150	72	Urea, Sodium nitrate	Rice flour	(160)
<i>Bacillus circulans</i> MTCC 7906	9.5	28	200	96	Beef extract Potato peel	glucose	(161)

Biochemistry of Alkaline Protease

Preparation of extracellular alkaline protease by enzyme concentration and purification

Purification of microbial proteases has received a great attention. A crude protein extract derived from some types of physical or chemical manipulation of the source will typically contain several types of contaminating molecules such as carbohydrates, lipids, nucleic acids, proteins, salts and other cellular debris. Separation of the protein fraction of the crude protein extract containing these contaminants is usually referred to as the capture step. One of the more popular methods of protein capture is the bulk precipitation from the crude extract (162). Precipitation also performs both purification and concentration steps. It is generally affected by the addition of reagents such as salt or an organic solvent that lower the solubility of the desired proteins in an aqueous solution.

Generally, purification procedures include 3-4 main steps e.g. Ammonium sulfate fractionation followed by dialysis (to remove excess salts and impurities) and then applying different sephadex chromatographic columns, using ion-exchange or adsorption chromatography and many cases performing the so called polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis technique (163). This protocol has been successfully employed in *Bacillus* sp. and *Pseudomonas* sp. (95). Joshi (35) used phenyl sepharose instead of DEAE-sephacryl where by the protease was completely retained by the matrix and all other impurities went into washing. The resultant bound protease was further eluted with 50% ethylene glycol.

Infact, Chromatography has been protease specific as Durham *et al* (164) purified proteases (AS and HS) from an alkalophilic *Bacillus* sp. strain GX6638 (ATCC 53278) by ion exchange chromatography that were distinguishable by their isoelectric point, molecular weight and electrophoretic

mobility. A thermostable alkaline protease was purified from an alkaliphilic thermophile *Bacillus* sp. B18 by using DEAE and CM-Toyopearl 650M column chromatographies (165). Mane and Bapat (166) isolated an alkaline protease from culture filtrate of *B. subtilis* NCIM 2713 by ammonium sulphate precipitation and was purified by gel filtration. Two novel extracellular serine proteases was reported in *B. sphaericus* (25). The crude enzyme was purified to homogeneity from the cell free culture filtrate by a combination of ultrafiltration, ammonium sulphate precipitation and chromatographic methods. Partial purification of protease enzyme which was performed using chilled acetone for enzyme precipitation (47) is one of the different methods that were applied for the protease purification.

Different workers have reported variable yield of purified (by enzyme precipitation followed by chromatographic separation) proteases. Kumar (153) purified an alkaline protease from *B. pumilis* MK6-5 by using ammonium sulphate precipitation, ion exchange and gel-filtration chromatographies, where in a 26.2% recovery of enzyme with 36.6 fold purification was recorded. Tang *et al* (167) treated crude enzyme of engineered strain of *Bacillus* sp. BA071 with ammonium sulphate fractionation and further purified it with CM-Sephadex-C-50 and Sephadex-G-75. The purity of enzyme was increased by 76.2 times. Thermostable serine alkaline protease from a newly isolated *B. subtilis* PE-11 was purified in a two step procedure involving ammonium sulphate precipitation (between 50%-70%) and sephadex G-200 gel permeation chromatography. The enzyme was purified 21-fold with a yield of 7.5% (154). The enzyme from *B. pseudofirmus* AL-89 grown on chicken feather was purified to electrophoretic homogeneity following ammonium sulphate precipitation (60% w/v), ion exchange, hydrophobic interaction and gel filtration chromatography. The yield and fold enzyme

purification was 44.1% and 43.7 times, respectively (40).

An alkaline protease producing haloalkaliphilic bacteria was isolated from west coast of India by Gupta et al (95). The protease secreted by this bacterium was purified 10 fold with 82% yield by a single step method on phenyl sepharose 6 fast flow column. The alkaline protease from *B. cereus* was purified to homogeneity by ammonium sulphate precipitation, concentrated by ultrafiltration followed by its anion exchange chromatography (168). Joo and Chang (119) carried out simple purification of an oxidant and SDS-stable alkaline protease produced by *B. clausii* I-52. The enzyme was purified to homogeneity with overall recovery of 79% and 10-fold purification from culture supernatant using Diaion HPA75, phenyl-Sepharose and DEAE-Sepharose column chromatographies. Kazan et al (169) observed 16-fold purification from culture filtrate of *B. clausii* GMBAE 42 by DEAE-cellulose chromatography, with a yield of 58%. In another report, a thermophilic neutral protease was purified and characterized from a thermophilic *Bacillus* strain HS08. The purification steps included ammonium sulphate precipitation (80% saturation), with columns of DEAE-Sepharose anion exchange chromatography and sephacryl S-100HR on AKTA purifier 100 protein liquid chromatography. This method gave a 4.25 fold increase of the specific activity and had a yield of 5.1% (170). Banik and Prakash (171) carried out ammonium sulphate fractionation at 80% saturation, concentration by ultrafiltration, anion exchange chromatography and gel filtration to have a 16-fold purification of alkaline protease. In another report, two alkaline proteases produced by marine *Bacillus* sp. MIG were observed. Two proteases were purified to homogeneity using acetone precipitation (two volumes of cold acetone), cation exchange chromatography on CM-Sepharose CL-6B, followed by gel filtration on Sephadex G-75 superfine. These steps

were very effective and combined to give overall purification of 19.3 and 16.1 fold for the protease 1 (Pro 1) and protease 2 (Pro 2), respectively (26). Darani et al (116) reported a new strain of *Bacillus* sp. from alkaline soil, whose purification was conducted by fractionation (55%), concentration and certain exchange chromatography. The yield and fold of enzyme purification was 24% and 50 times respectively. Alkaline protease enzyme from *B. pumilis* CBS was purified by using salt precipitation (between 40% and 60%) and gel filtration HPLC. The yield and fold enzyme purification were 12% and 38 times, (53) respectively.

Protease from *B. subtilis* KO strain (172) was precipitated by using ammonium sulphate fractionation (20%) and further purified by column chromatography (Sephadex G-200, mesh 200 μ) techniques. Fakhfakh et al (136) purified protease produced by *B. licheniformis* RPK to homogeneity from the culture supernatant by a 3-step procedure. The keratinolytic protease was precipitated by $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ between 40 and 60% (32,142 U/mg of protein) which was then subjected to gel filtration on a Sephadex G-100 column and DEAE-cellulose. The elution profiles of the protease and proteins from Sephadex G-100 yielded a single peak of protease activity with an increase of 4.4 fold in specific activity and 52.8% recovery. A 6.8 fold purification of TC4 protease from *B. alcalophilus* TCCC11004, 5.34 fold alkaline protease purification of *B. firmus* Tap5 and 13 fold purification of a thermophilic alkaline protease from *Bacillus* sp. were reported by Cheng et al (102), Joshi (35), (141), respectively by employing gel filtration, ammonium sulphate or acetone precipitation protocols.

The molecular weights of alkaline proteases generally range from 15 to 35 kDa (132, 154, 173) with few reports of higher molecular weights of 36.0 kDa (164), 42 kDa from *Bacillus* sp. PS719 (174) and a very high (90 kDa) from *B. subtilis* (175). Recent reports on different isolated species for alkaline

proteases production and its purification studies are summarized in table 5. strategies along with results of respective

Table 5 Recent purification strategies adopted for alkaline proteases from different microorganisms

Microorganism	Isolation /Procurement	Purification Technique	Fold purification	Molecular weight	Reference
<i>B. licheniformis</i> MP1	shrimp waste	Ultrafiltration + sephadex G-100 gel filtration + Mono Q-sepharose ion exchange chromatography	3.9	30	(176)
<i>B. subtilis</i>	Enzyme Biotechnology laboratory, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Pakistan	Ammonium sulphate precipitation (40-70% saturation) + dialysis + sephadex G-100 column chromatography	1.9	27	(177)
<i>B. cereus</i> 1173900	Waste water from tanning industry	Ammonium sulphate precipitapn (70%) + dialysis + sephadex G-100	53.64	66	(178)
<i>Serratia marcescens</i> S3-R1	Korean ginseng rhizosphere.	Ammonium sulfate precipitation + DEAE-Sepharose anion-exchange chromatograph + Mono Q chromatography	-	50	(179)
<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	soil	Ammonium sulfate precipitation + DEAE-cellulose ion-exchange chromatography + gel filtration sephadex G-200	P1=13.6 3 P2= 7.72	P1=28 P2=25	(180)
<i>Saccharomycopsis fibuligera</i> strain R64	Tape Indonesian fermented food	50% ammonium sulfate precipitation + dialysis + gel filtration G 100	20	97	(181)
<i>Planomicrobium</i> sp. L-2	digestive tract of <i>Octopus variabilis</i>	ammonium sulfate precipitation, dialysis and enrichment, DEAE-Sephadex A50 anion-exchange chromatography, and Sephadex G-100 gel chromatography	1.7	61.4	(182)
<i>Geobacillus stearothermophilus</i> B-1172	---	Ammonium sulfate precipitation + dialysis + ion exchange chromatography	13.7	39	(183)
<i>Bacillus circulans</i> MTCC 7906	Vegetable waste	Ammonium sulphate precipitation + dialysis + DEAE cellulose ion exchange chromatography + PEG concentrated	22	40	(20)

Characterization of purified alkaline protease for kinetic parameters

Effect of pH

Enzymes are amphoteric molecules containing a large number of acid and basic groups, mainly located on their surface. The charges on these groups vary according to their acid dissociation constants and pH of their environment. This affects the net charge on the enzymes and the distribution of charges on their exterior surfaces, in addition to the reactivity of the catalytically active groups. These effects are especially important in the neighborhood of the active sites, which will overall affect the activity, structural stability and solubility of the enzyme (184). In general, all currently used detergent-compatible proteases are alkaline in nature with a high pH optimum, therefore they fit into the pH of laundry detergents, which is generally in the range of 8 to 12. Therefore, most of the commercially available subtilisin-type proteases are also active in the pH range of 8-12 (92). A good example for this is the well-known detergent enzymes, subtilisin Carlsberg and subtilisin Novo or BPN which show maximum activity at pH 10.5 (185).

Alkaline proteases of the genus *Bacillus* show an optimal activity and a good stability at high alkaline pH values (186). The optimum pH range of *Bacillus* alkaline proteases is generally between pH 9 and 11, with a few exceptions of higher pH optima of 11.5 (153), 11-12 (25, 107) and 12-13 (187).

Effect of temperature

The heat stability of enzymes is affected by at least two factors, either alone or in combination. The first one is the primary structure of the enzyme. A high content of hydrophobic amino acids in the enzyme molecule provides a compact structure, which is not denatured easily by a change in the external environment. In addition, disulfide bridges and other bonds provide a high resistance both to heat inactivation and chemical denaturation. Secondly, specific

components such as polysaccharides and divalent cations, if any, can stabilize the molecule (188).

Even though there is no firm evidence to suggest that thermostable enzymes are necessarily derived from thermophilic organisms, there is a greater chance of finding thermostable proteins from non-thermophilic bacteria (56). Therefore, a wide range of microbial proteases from thermophilic species has been extensively purified and characterized. These include *Thermus* sp., *Desulfurococcus* strain Tok12S1 and *Bacillus* sp. Among these, alkaline proteases derived from alkalophilic bacilli, are known to be active and stable in highly alkaline conditions. The earliest thermophilic and alkalophilic *Bacillus* sp. was *B. stearothermophilus* strain F1 isolated (189), which was stable at 60°C (190). Further studies on microbial alkaline proteases have been done in view of their structural-function relationship and industrial applications, as they need stable biocatalysts capable of withstanding harsh conditions of operation (56).

Generally alkaline proteases produced from alkaliphilic *Bacillus* are known to be active over a wide range of temperature. The optimum temperatures of alkaline proteases range from 40 to 80°C. In addition, the enzyme from an obligatory alkalophilic *Bacillus* P-2 showed an exceptionally high optimum temperature of 90°C. The protease also had good thermostability being stable at 90°C for more than 1 h and retained 95 and 37% of its activity at 99°C (boiling) and 121°C (autoclaving temperature), respectively. *Bacillus* P-2 was the only mesophile reported until 2001, which produced a proteolytic enzyme that was stable even at autoclaving (121°C) and boiling temperatures (135).

Effect of enzyme and substrate concentration

Enzyme concentration is an important factor in determining the rate of reaction. The enzyme activity is directly proportional to

enzyme concentration at a particular substrate concentration. Hence, when all enzyme sites are saturated for the substrate, there is no further increase in enzyme activity even with increase in enzyme concentration.

A number of studies revealed that concentration of enzyme and substrate dependent on the type and speed of alkaline protease producing microorganisms. Researchers found 50% protease (of the reaction mixture) as the optimum for alkaline protease activity in the reaction mixture (2.0 ml) containing 0.05 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5), casein and enzyme (1.0%, 1.0 ml) in case of *B. polymyxa* B-17 (191). Huang *et al* (192) also revealed that 1.0 ml (50%) is optimum for protease activity at 2.0% casein in Bongsuan-NaOH buffer (pH 9.8) and temperature of 50°C in *B. pumilis*. Caseinolytic activity was estimated by using different enzyme concentrations (0.05-0.5 ml) in a reaction mixture of 3 ml, 0.1 ml of enzyme that constitutes 3.33% of reaction mixture produced maximum protease activity (173). Similarly, in another report, Ahmed *et al* (177) reported 33.3% protease as optimal for alkaline protease activity in *Bacillus* sp. GUS1 and *B. subtilis*, respectively.

Enzymes are natural catalysts that speed up the chemical reactions. However, the speed of any fastidious reaction being catalysed by a particular enzyme can only reach a certain maximum value. This rate is known as V_{max} while, K_m can define the concentration of substrate at which half of the maximal velocity (V_{max}) is obtained. The relationship between rate of reaction and concentration of substrate depends on the affinity of the enzyme for its substrate and is usually expressed as the K_m (Michaelis constant) of the enzyme. An enzyme with low K_m has a greater affinity for its substrate. An alkaline protease is highly substrate specific and exhibits maximum activity towards casein as substrate (193). Adinarayana *et al* (154)

reported that proteases have a high level of hydrolytic activity for casein as substrate and poor to moderate hydrolysis of BSA and egg albumin, respectively.

Among the different studies on alkaline protease kinetics, Mane and Bapat (166) reported a K_m value of 2.5 mg/ml for alkaline protease from *B. subtilis* NCIM 2713. Kumar (153) observed K_m and K_{cat} values for alkaline protease of *B. pumilis* MK6-5 with synthetic substrates at 37°C and pH 8.0 as 1.1 mmol l⁻¹ and 624 s⁻¹ for Glu-Gly-Ala-Phe-pNA and 3.7 mmol l⁻¹ and 826 s⁻¹ for Glu-Ala-Ala-Ala-pNA, respectively. The kinetic data revealed that small aliphatic and aromatic residues were the preferred residues at the P1 position. Gupta *et al* (95) reported an alkaline protease producing haloalkaliphilic *Bacillus* sp. that had K_m and V_{max} of 2 mg/ml and 289.8 µg/min, respectively. Joo and Chang (119) determined the K_m (83.9 micromol l⁻¹) and K_{cat} (238.6 s⁻¹) values for alkaline protease from a halo-tolerant *B. clausii* I-52 and Kazan *et al* (169) observed K_m (0.655 µM) and K_{cat} (4.21 × 10³ min⁻¹) values for *B. clausii* GMBAE 42. Patel *et al* (24) reported the K_m and V_{max} of an extracellular alkaline protease from a novel haloalkaliphilic *Bacillus* sp. (Ve1) as 0.153 g/100 ml and 454 U/ml, respectively. The kinetic parameters of serine alkaline protease from *B. pumilis* CBS (SAPB) was determined (53). The K_m , V_{max} and K_{cat} values of SAPB for casein (natural substrate) were 0.4 mM, 27,160 U/mg and 18,106 min⁻¹, respectively. Its deduced catalytic efficiency (k_{cat}/K_m) was found to be 45,265 min⁻¹ mM⁻¹, which was 4.77, 2.73 and 2.11 times higher than those of SC, SB 309 and BPN', respectively. In addition, the K_m and k_{cat} values of SAPB for N-succinyl-L-Ala-Ala-Pro-Phe-p-nitroanilide (AAPF), as synthetic substrate, were 0.3 mM and 44,100 min⁻¹, respectively with a deduced K_{cat}/K_m of 147,000 min⁻¹ mM⁻¹, which was 2.21, 1.88 and 1.68 times higher than those of SB 309, SC and BPN', respectively. These results strongly suggest that SAPB is the most promising candidate

for cleansing power of laundry detergent and various other biotechnological applications.

Recently, Deng *et al* (18) observed the kinetic parameters of purified recombinant AprB towards different substrates. Alkaline protease enzyme of *Bacillus* sp. B001 indicated its maximum catalytic velocities (V_{max}) towards casein (natural substrate), azocasein (modified substrate) and AAPF (synthetic peptide substrate) of 12.54, 102.54 and 242.09×10^3 U/mg respectively with a substrate preference of azocasin > casein > AAPF. The deduced K_{cat}/K_m (catalytic efficiency) values of AprB for casein, azocasein and AAPF were found to be 57.42, 906.31 and 151.01×10^3 $\text{min}^{-1} \text{mM}^{-1}$ respectively. These high catalytic efficiencies of AprB strongly indicate that it is a potential candidate for use as a laundry additive and other commercial applications (194).

The protease from *B. circulans* showed K_m of 0.597 mg ml^{-1} and V_{max} of $13825 \mu\text{M min}^{-1}$ towards casein as a substrate at 70°C (195). The K_m , K_{cat} values of *B.licheniformis* MP1 purified alkaline protease were 0.53 mM and $12.7 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ respectively using casein as substrate (176). Using casein as substrate, the alkaline protease enzyme from *B. subtilis* showed maximum activity (V_{max}) of 148 U/ml with its corresponding K_m value of $58 \mu\text{M}$ (177). Furthermore, kinetic constants (K_m and V_{max}) for extracellular purified alkaline protease of *B. licheniformis* NCIM-2042 was determined (39) using Lineweaver-Burk plot as 0.01078 g/100 ml and 182.9 U , respectively.

Hence, there is a large variation in K_m and V_{max} values, revealed that optimum concentration of substrate is species specific.

Effect of metal ions and inhibitors on the alkaline protease activity

Various kind of metal ions, reagents and osmolytes have been reported to influence the enzyme activity of proteases, their pH and temperature stability. Alkaline

proteases isolated from different fungal and bacterial sources behave differently in the presence of mono or divalent ions. Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} have been found to enhance the enzymatic activity of alkaline protease isolated from *B. licheniformis* (196). It was found that Hg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions inhibit the proteolytic activity of alkaline protease of *Bacillus* sp. JB99 (47) whereas Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mg^{2+} had stimulating effect on the enzyme activity. Ca^{2+} ion dependent activity is thought to be attributed to its involvement in stabilization of the protease molecular structure derived from *Bacillus* sp. (60, 174).

In case of alkaline protease of *Bacillus* sp. RGR 14, a two-fold enhancement in protease activity was observed in the presence of Mn^{2+} (1mM), however, the enzyme was strongly inhibited up to 90% in the presence of 10 mM Hg^{2+} and Cu^{2+} (173). Many alkaline proteases are reported to be inhibited by Hg^{2+} and Ag^+ (26). Fe^{2+} was found to be the most effective stimulator while Cu^{2+} was least effective for the alkaline protease of *Bacillus* sp. (197). The activity of protease DHAP of *B. pumilus* was enhanced by Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Na^{2+} and inhibited by Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} (192). Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Mn^{2+} ions positively regulated the enzyme activity in *B. circulans* (195) and *B. alcalophilus* TCCC11004 (102). It is believed that these cations protect the enzyme against thermal denaturation and play a role in maintaining the active conformation of the enzyme at higher temperatures.

Most of the fungal and bacterial alkaline proteases have been found to be serine proteases as these are inhibited by PMSF and DFP, which sulfonated the essential serine residue in the active site and resulted in the complete loss of its activity (102,154,172). Some of these serine proteases have been found to be metal ions dependent as these are inhibited by certain metal chelating agents such as EDTA etc. (173,193). Contrary to these reports, a few alkaline proteases have not been found to be

inhibited by both or either PMSF or EDTA (25, 31,177).

Scale Up Studies of Alkaline Protease Production

In order to scale up protease production from microorganisms, biochemical and process engineers use several strategies to obtain high yields of proteases. Controlled batch and fed batch fermentation using simultaneous control of glucose, ammonium ion concentration, oxygen tension, pH and salt availability (93) and chemostat cultures have been successfully employed for improving protease production by a number of microorganisms.

Among the different case studies, *B. subtilis* from tannery waste was isolated (93), produced alkaline protease (pH 8.5) in a stirred tank fermenter at 37°C with the dissolved oxygen tension at 40% air saturation. Alkaline protease yield from *B. mojavensis* was improved upto 4-fold under semi batch and fed batch operations by separating biomass and protease production phases using intermittent de-repression and induction during the growth of organism (94). Moreover, an enhanced production of alkaline protease by an engineered strain BA071 in a 5L fermentor was reported. It was found that the maximum activity of alkaline protease reached 24,480 U/ml in 40 hours of fermentation by combination of enhancing aeration and regulating the agitation rate (167). Kumar *et al* (198) found a 5-fold increase in alkaline protease yields (31899 U/ml) at a lower production time of 45h, aeration of 1vvm and agitation of 400 rev/min at 37°C using arrow root starch casein medium (pH 10.2). Besides the improved yield, time of production was also reduced by 27 hours. Earlier, protease production in bioreactor at high agitation rate of 360-600 rpm have also been reported by Moon *et al* (86) in *B. firmus*. Alkaline protease production by a marine haloalkalophilic *B. clausii* was optimized in a bioreactor. The isolate produced maximum protease yields (15000 U/ml) under

submerged fermentation conditions at 42°C for 40 hours with aeration of 1.5 vvm and agitation of 400 rev/min.

Similarly, Haq and Mukhtar (199) used a 7.5-L bioreactor for alkaline protease production (pH 9.0, 35°C, 175 rpm) by *B. subtilis* and Saurabh *et al* (139) employed a 10 L fermentor (Bio-flow IV, NBS, USA) for alkaline protease production (pH 7.0, 37°C, 350 rpm, 0.5 0.5 vvm) by *Bacillus* sp. and reported enzyme production of 3208 U/ml in 18 h. Thereafter, a decline in the protease production was observed in the bioreactor. Similar cessation in protease production has been reported (86, 92), once a maximum amount of the enzyme is produced during the run. Although, there are several theories such as autolysis (200) and protease degradation by some proteases present on the cell surface on nitrogen starved cells (134, 155), the exact mechanism is yet not known. Laxman *et al* (81) reported the production of alkaline protease from *Condibolous coronatus* in 100 L fermenter with soyabean as optimum in concentrations of 2-3% as best inducer with diammonium hydrogen phosphate, casamino acids and Hi-media peptone gave activities comparable to yeast extract. The ammonium sulphate saturated enzyme was found to be stable upto two years. Researchers (139) revealed maximum of 3208 U/mL of protease from *Bacillus* was produced in 18 h in a 10L bioreactor. The enzyme has temperature and pH optima of 60°C and 9.5, respectively. However, the temperature stability range is from 20-90 °C and pH stability range is from 6.0-12.0. The protease was completely inhibited by PhenylMethylSulfonyl Fluoride (PMSF) and Diodopropyl FluoroPhosphate (DFP), with little increase (10-15%) in the production of upon addition of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺. Irfan *et al* (201) showed that *Bacillus subtilis* M-21 was used for the production of alkaline protease in 2 L jar fermenter with working volume 1.5 L. Soybean meal was used as choice of substrate due to its high nitrogen contents. The effect of different process parameters

(pH, temperature, agitation and aeration) and their relationship with each other was studied during fermentation process. Highest protease production (896.5 ± 1.5 PU/ml) was obtained at optimum pH 10, temperature 37°C , agitation rate 300 rpm and at aeration 2 ml/min. The maximum protease activity was obtained from *P. aeruginosa* MCM B-327 with soybean meal 1%, tryptone 1%, initial medium pH 7, agitation rate 250 rpm, aeration rate 0.75 vvm and fermentation temperature 30°C , under submerged fermentation conditions (SmF). The protease productivity at 10 and 120L fermenters was found to be 16,021 and 9,975 $\text{UL}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ respectively (202).

Conclusion

In a moderately small time, recent biotechnological approaches have developed significantly from laboratory inquisitiveness towards commercialization. Recent trends in microbiological ideas and biotechnology have fashioned an encouraging niche for the advancement of proteases and would sustain their applications to give a sustainable environment for the improvement of mankind. Alkaline protease carries vast potential in diverse industries such as detergent, leather, food and pharmaceutical industry. In the present scenario, it's need of an hour to explore novel microorganisms for enzyme production which should have adaptable capacity to accomplish demand of industry. For industrial uses, enzyme production requires: isolation and characterization of novel microbes (strains) by utilizing cheaper carbon and nitrogen sources. Furthermore, the enzyme (alkaline protease) activity is influenced by various environmental factors, for instance pH, Temperature and ionic strength of the production medium. Besides, keeping in mind the stringent conditions of industrial processes, the genetic and protein engineering could participate an essential role for modifying the enzyme's properties in order to produce enzymes at large scale.

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Conflict of Interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Asha B, Palaniswamy M. Optimization of alkaline protease production by *Bacillus cereus* FT 1 isolated from soil. J Appl Pharma Sci. 2018; 8(2): 119-27.
2. Cui H, Yang M, Wang L, Xian CJ. Identification of a new marine bacterial strain SD8 and optimization of its culture conditions for producing alkaline protease. PLoS One. 2015; 10: e0146067.
3. Sumantha A, Larroche C, Pandey A. microbiology and industrial biotechnology of food-grade proteases: A perspective. Food Technol Biotechnol. 2006; 44: 211-20.
4. Gupta R, Beg QK, Lorenz P. Bacterial alkaline proteases: molecular approaches and industrial applications. Appl Microbiol Biotechnol. 2002a; 59: 15-32.
5. Whitaker JR. Principles of enzymology for the food science, Ed. Board, New York, 1994; pp. 469-97.
6. Kumar R, Sharma KM, Vats S, Gupta A. Production, partial purification and characterization of alkaline protease from *Bacillus aryabhatai* K3. Int J Adv Pharm Biol Chem. 2014; 3(2): 290-98.
7. Ferrari E, Jarnagin AS, Schmidt BF. Commercial production of extracellular enzymes. In: Sonenshine A L, Hoch J A and Losick R (ed) *Bacillus subtilis and other grampositive bacteria*. American Society for Microbiology Press, Washington, D.C. 1993; p 917-38.
8. Kocher GS, Mishra S. Immobilization of *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 7906 for enhanced production of alkaline protease under batch and packed bed fermentation conditions. Internet J Microbiol 2009; 7:(2).
9. Genckal H, Tari C. Alkaline protease production from alkalophilic *Bacillus* sp. isolated from natural habitats. Enzyme Microb Technol. 2006; 39: 703-10.
10. Saeki K, Ozaki K, Kobayashi T, Ito S. Detergent alkaline proteases: enzymatic properties, genes, and crystal structures. J

- Biosci Bioeng 2007; 103: 501-8.
11. Bhaskar N, Sudeepa ES, Rashmi HN, Selvi AT. Partial purification and characterization of protease of *Bacillus proteolyticus*-CFR3001 isolated from fish processing waste and its antibacterial activities. *Bioresour Technol.* 2007; 98: 2758-64.
 12. Deng A, Wu J, Zhang Y, Zhang G, Wen T. Purification and characterization of a surfactant-stable high-alkaline protease from *Bacillus* sp. B001. *Bioresour Technol.* 2010; 101: 7100-06.
 13. Jellouli K, Bellaaj OG, Ayed HB, Manni L, Agrebi R, Nasri M. Alkaline-protease from *Bacillus licheniformis* MP1: Purification, characterization and potential application as a detergent additive and for shrimp waste deproteinization. *Process Biochem.* 2011; 46: 1248-56.
 14. Sharma KM, Kumar R, Panwar S, Kumar A. Microbial alkaline proteases: Optimization of production parameters and their properties. *J Gent Eng Biotechnol.* 2017; 15: 115-26.
 15. Adinarayana K, Jyothi B, Ellaiah P. Production of alkaline protease with immobilized cells of *Bacillus subtilis* PE-11 in various matrices by entrapment technique. *AAPS Pharm Sci Tech.* 2005; 6(3).
 16. Kaur I, Kocher GS. Production of alkaline protease by *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 7906 using agricultural by-products. *Indian J of Ecol.* 2011; 38(2): 291-93.
 17. Sarker P K, Talukdar S A, Deb P, Sayem S M A, Mohsina K. Optimization and partial characterization of culture conditions for the production of alkaline protease from *Bacillus licheniformis* P003. *Springer-Plus.* 2013; 2: 506.
 18. Deng A, Wu J, Zhang G, Wen T. Molecular and structural characterization of a surfactant-stable high-alkaline protease AprB with a novel structural feature unique to subtilisin family. *Biochimie.* 2011; 93: 783-91.
 19. Cheng SW, Wang YF, Wang ML. Statistical Optimization of Medium Compositions for Alkaline Protease Production by Newly Isolated *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*. *Chem Biochem Eng Q.* 2012; 26(3): 225-31.
 20. Kocher GS, Joshi N. Production and Partial Purification of Alkaline Protease from *Bacillus circulans* MTCC 7906 using Potato Peel as Substrate. *Indian J Microbiol Res.* 2015; 2(1): 7-13.
 21. Benkiar A, Nadia ZJ, Badis A, Rebzani F, Soraya BT, Rekik H, Naili B, Ferradji FZ, Bejar S, Jaouadi B. Biochemical and molecular characterization of a thermo- and detergent-stable alkaline serine keratinolytic protease from *Bacillus circulans* strain DZ100 for detergent formulations and feather-biodegradation process. *Int Biodeter Biodegrad.* 2013; 83: 129-38.
 22. Purohit M, Singh SP. Cloning, over expression and functional attributes of serine proteases from *Oceanobacillus iheyensis* O.M.A18 and Haloalkaliphilic bacterium O.M.E12. *Process Biochem.* 2014; 49: 61-68.
 23. Horikoshi K. Production of alkaline enzymes by alkalophilic microorganisms, Part 1. Alkaline protease produced by *Bacillus* no. 221. *Agric Biol Chem.* 1971; 35: 1407-14.
 24. Patel R, Mittal D, Singh SP. Extracellular alkaline protease from a newly isolated haloalkaliphilic *Bacillus* sp.: Production and optimization. *Process Biochem.* 2005; 40: 3569-75.
 25. Singh J, Batra N, Sobti RC. Serine alkaline protease from newly isolated *Bacillus* sp. SSR1. *Process Biochem.* 2001; 36: 781-85.
 26. Gouda MK. Optimization and purification of alkaline protease produced by marine *Bacillus* sp. MIG newly isolated from Eastern harbour of Alexandria. *Pol J Microbio.* 2006; 55(2): 119-26.
 27. Tari C, Genckal H, Tokatli F. Optimization of a growth medium using a statistical approach for the production of an alkaline protease from a newly isolated *Bacillus* sp. L21. *Process Biochem.* 2006; 41: 659-65.
 28. Hindhumathi M, Vijayalakshmi S, Thankamani V. Optimization and cultural characterization of alkalophilic protease producing *Bacillus* sp. GPA4. *Res Biotechnol.* 2011; 2(4): 13-19.
 29. Das G, Prasad MP. Isolation, purification and mass production of protease enzyme from *Bacillus subtilis*. *Int Res J microbial.* 2010; 1(2): 26-31.
 30. Asif M, Hussain A, Ali M A, Rasool M. Scale up studies for the production of protease enzyme using *Bacillus subtilis* adopting response surface methodology. *Afr J Microbiol Res.* 2012; 6(9): 2120-28.
 31. Ramakrishna DPN, Gopi RN, Rajagopal SV. Purification and properties of an extracellular alkaline protease produced by *Bacillus subtilis* (MTTC N0-10110). *Int J Biotechnol Biochem.* 2010; 6(4): 493-504.
 32. Reddy MN, Kumar CG, Swathi K, Nagamani

- B, Venkateshwar S, Rao LV. Extracellular alkaline protease production from isolated *Bacillus subtilis* svr-07 by using submerged fermentation. *Int J Pharma Res Dev.* 2011; 3(1): 216-23.
33. Akcan N, Uyar F. Production of extracellular alkaline protease from *Bacillus subtilis* RSKK96 with solid state fermentation. *EurAsia J Biosci.* 2011; 5: 64-72.
34. Landau NS, Egorov NS, Gornova B, Krasovskaya SB, Virnik AD. Immobilization of *Bacillus firmus* cell in cellulose triacetate fibres and films and their use in protease biosynthesis. *Appl Biochem Microbiol.* 1992; 28: 84-88.
35. Joshi BH. Purification and characterization of a novel protease from *Bacillus firmus* Tap5 isolated from Tannery Waste. *J Appl Sci Res.* 2010; 6(8): 1068-76.
36. Boyer EW, Byng GS. *Bacillus proteolyticus* species produces an alkaline protease. 1996; U.S. Patent, 551891.
37. Hotha S, Banik RM. Production of alkaline protease by *Bacillus thuringiensis* H14 in aqueous two-phase systems. *J Chem Technol Biotechnol.* 1997; 69: 5-10.
38. Enshasy EH, Abuoul-Enein A, Helmy S, El Azaly Y. Optimization of the industrial production of alkaline protease by *Bacillus licheniformis* in different production scales. *Aust J of Basic and Appl Sci.* 2008; 2(3): 583-93.
39. Bhunia B, Dutta D, Chaudhuri S. Extracellular alkaline protease from *Bacillus licheniformis* NCIM-2042: Improving enzyme activity assay and characterization. *Eng Life Sci.* 2011; 11(1): 1-9.
40. Gessesse A, Hatti-Kaul R, Gashe BA, Mattiasson B. Novel alkaline proteases from alkaliphilic bacteria grown on chicken feather. *Enzyme Microb Technol.* 2003; 32: 519-24.
41. Bhatiya R, Jadeja GR. Optimization of environmental and nutritional factors for alkaline protease production. *Elec J Environ Agri Food Chem.* 2010; 9(3): 594-99.
42. Sundararajan S, Kannan CN, Chittibabu S. Alkaline protease from *Bacillus cereus* VITSN04: Potential application as a dehairing agent. *J Biosci Bioeng.* 2011; 111(2): 128-33.
43. Sharmin S, Towhid Hossain MD, Anwat MN. Isolation and characterization of a protease producing bacteria *Bacillus amovivorus* and optimization of some factors of culture conditions for protease production. *J Biol Sci.* 2005; 5(3): 358-62.
44. Mahendran S, Shankaralingam S, Shankar T, Vijayabaskar P. Alkalophilic protease production from Estuarine *Bacillus aquamaris*. *World J Fis Marin Sci.* 2010; 2(5): 436-43.
45. Oskouie SFG, Tabandehb F, Yakhchalib B, Eftekhari F. Response surface optimization of medium composition for alkaline protease production by *Bacillus clausii*. *Biochem Eng J.* 2008; 39(1): 37-42.
46. Singh J, Vohra RM, Sahoo DK. Enhanced production of alkaline proteases by *Bacillus sphaericus* using fed-batch culture. *Process Biochem.* 2004; 39(9): 1093-1101.
47. Johanvesly B, Naik GR. Studies on production of thermostable alkaline protease from thermophilic and alkaliphilic *Bacillus* sp. JB99 in a chemically defined medium. *Process Biochem.* 2001; 37: 139-44.
48. Do Nascimento WCA, Martins MLL. Production and properties of an extracellular protease from thermophilic *Bacillus* sp. *Braz J Microbiol.* 2004; 35: 91-96.
49. Vijayalakshmi S, Venkatkumar S, Thankamani V. Screening of alkalophilic thermophilic protease isolated from *Bacillus* RV.B2.90 for industrial applications. *Res Biotechnol* 2011; 2(3): 32-41.
50. Sellami-Kamoun A, Haddar A, Ali NEH, Ghorbel-Frikha B, Kanoun S, Nasri M. (2008) Stability of thermostable alkaline protease from *Bacillus licheniformis* RP1 in commercial solid laundry detergent formulations. *Microbiol Res.* 2008; 163: 299-306.
51. Manachini PL, Fortina MG, Parini C. Thermostable alkaline protease produced by *Bacillus thermoruber*- A new species of *Bacillus*. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 1998; 28: 409-13.
52. Sookkheo B, Sinchaikul S, Phutrakul S, Chen ST. Purification and characterization of the highly thermostable proteases from *Bacillus stearothermophilus* TLS33. *Protein Expr Purif.* 2000; 20: 142-51.
53. Jaouadi B, Ellouz-Chaabouni S, Rhimi M, Bejar S. Biochemical and molecular characterization of a detergent-stable serine alkaline protease from *Bacillus pumilus* CBS with high catalytic efficiency. *Biochimie.* 2008; 90: 1291-1305
54. Tsuchiya K, Nakamura Y, Sakashita H, Kimura T. Purification and characterization of thermostable alkaline protease from

- alkalophilic *Thermoactinomyces* sp. HS682. *Biosci Biotechnol Biochem.* 1992; 56: 246-50.
55. Phadatare SU, Deshpande VV, Srinivasan MC. High activity alkaline protease from *Conidiobolus coronatus* (NCL 86.8.20): Enzyme production and compatibility with commercial detergents. *Enzyme Microb Technol.* 1993; 15: 72-76.
56. Rahman RNZA, Razak CN, Ampon K, Basri M, Yunus WMZW, Salleh AB. Purification and characterization of a heat-stable alkaline protease from *Bacillus stearothersophilus* F1. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 1994; 40: 822-27.
57. Hawumba JF, Theron J, Brozel VS. Thermophilic protease producing *Geobacillus* from Buranga hot springs in Western Uganda. *Curr Microbiol.* 2002; 45: 144-50.
58. Vasantha ST, Thankappan A. Optimization of cultural conditions for the production of an extracellular protease by *Pseudomonas* species. *Int Curr Pharm J.* 2012; 2(1): 1-6.
59. Venugopal M, Saramma AV. (2006) Characterization of alkaline protease from *Vibrio fluviialis* strain VM 10 isolated from mangrove sediment sample and its application as a laundry detergent additive. *Process Biochem.* 2006; 41: 1239-43.
60. Sana B, Ghosh D, Saha M, Mukherjee J. Purification and characterization of a salt, solvent, detergent and bleach tolerant protease from a new gamma-Proteobacterium isolated from the marine environment of the Sundarbans. *Process Biochem.* 2006; 41: 208-15.
61. Chakrabarti SK, Matsumura N, Ranu RS. Purification and characterization of an extracellular alkaline serine protease from *Aspergillus terreus* (IJIRA 6.2). *Curr Microbiol.* 2000; 40(4): 239-44.
62. Banerjee R, Bhattacharyya BC. Optimization of multiple inducers effect on protease biosynthesis by *Rhizopus oryzae*. *Bioprocess Eng.* 1992; 7: 225-28.
63. Poza M, De Miguel T, Sieiro C, Villa TG. Characterization of broad pH range proteases of *Candida caseinolytica*. *J Appl Microbiol.* 2001; 91: 916-21.
64. Bajaj B, Sharma P. Thermotolerant extracellular protease from a newly isolated *Streptomyces* sp. DP2. *New Biotech.* 2011; 28(6): 725-32.
65. Moreira KA, Porto TS, Teixeira MFS, Porto ALF, Filho JLL. New alkaline protease from *Nocardioopsis* sp.: Partial purification and characterization. *Process Biochem.* 2003; 39: 67-72.
66. De Azeredo LAI, De Lima MB, Coelho RRR, Freire DMG. A low-cost fermentation medium for thermophilic protease production by *Streptomyces* sp. 594 using feather meal and corn steep liquor. *Curr Microbiol.* 2006; 53: 335-39.
67. Abbas CA, Groves S, Gander JE. Isolation, purification and properties of *Penicillium charlesii* alkaline protease. *J Bacteriol.* 1989; 171(10):5630-37.
68. Antranikian G, Klingenberg M. Thermostable protease from *Staphylothermus*. 1991; PCT Pat Appl WO 9119791.
69. Kitano K, Morita S, Kuriyama M, Maejima K. Alkaline protease gene from a *Fusarium* sp. *Eur Pat Appl.* 1992; EP 0519229.
70. Dixit G, Verma SC. Production of alkaline protease by *Penicillium griseofulvin*. *Ind J Microbiol.* 1995; 3(4): 257-60.
71. Dozie INS, Okeke CN, Unaeze NC. A thermostable, alkaline active, keratinolytic proteinase from *Chrysosporium keratinophilum*. *World J Microbiol Biotechnol.* 1994; 10: 563-67.
72. Larcher G, Cimon B, Symoens F, Tronchin G, Chabasse D, Bouchara JP. A 33 kDa serine proteinase from *Scedosporium apiospermum*. *Biochem J.* 1996; 315: 119-26.
73. Luisetti M, Piccioni PO, Dyne K, Donnini M, Bulgheroni A, Pasturenzi L, Donnetta AM, Peona V. Some properties of the alkaline proteinase from *Aspergillus mellus*. *Int J Tissue React.* 1991; 13: 187-92.
74. Dubey R, Adhikary S, Kumar J, Sinha N. Isolation, production, purification, assay and characterization of alkaline protease enzyme from *Aspergillus niger* and its compatibility with commercial detergents. *Dev Microbiol Mol Biol.* 2010; 1(1): 75-94.
75. Wang SL, Chen YH, Wang CL, Yen YH, Chern MK. Purification and characterization of a serine protease extracellularly produced by *Aspergillus fumigatus* in a shrimp and crab shell powder medium. *Enzyme Microb Technol.* 2005; 36: 660-65.
76. Chakraborty R, Srinivasan M. Production of a thermostable alkaline protease by a new *Pseudomonas* sp. by solid substrate fermentation. *J Microb Biotechnol.* 1993; 8: 7-16.
77. Tremacoldi CR, Monti R, Selistre-De-Araujo HS, Carmona EC. Purification and properties

- of an alkaline protease of *Aspergillus clavatus*. World J Microbiol Biotechnol. 2007; 23: 295-99.
78. Charles P, Devanathan V, Anbu P, Ponnuswamy MN, Kalaichelvan PT, Ki Hur B. Purification, characterization and crystallization of an extracellular alkaline protease from *Aspergillus nidulans* HA-10. J Basic Microbiol. 2008; 48: 347-52.
79. Guo JP, Ma Y. High-level expression, purification and characterization of recombinant *Aspergillus oryzae* alkaline protease in *Pichia pastoris*. Protein Exp Purification. 2008; 58(2): 301-08.
80. Negi S, Banerjee R. Optimization of culture parameters to enhance production of amylase and protease from *Aspergillus awamori* in a single fermentation. Afr J Biochem Res. 2010; 4: 73-80.
81. Laxman RS, Sonawane AP, More SV, Rao BS, Rele MV, Jogdand VV, Deshpande VV, Rao MB. Optimization and scale up of production of alkaline protease from *Conidiobolus coronatus*. Process Biochem. 2005; 40: 3152-58.
82. Abidi F, Limam F, Marzouki MN. Production of *Botrytis cinerea* using economic raw materials: Assay as biode detergent. Process Biochem. 2008; 43:1202-08.
83. Lazim H, Mankai H, Slama N, Barkallah I, Limam F. Production and optimization of thermophilic alkaline protease in solid-state fermentation by *Streptomyces* sp. CN902. J Ind Microbiol Biotech. 2009; 36(4): 531-37.
84. Ahmed AS, Al-domany AR, El-Shayeb MAN, Radwan HH, Saleh AS. Optimization, immobilization of extracellular alkaline protease and characterization of its enzymatic properties. Res J Agri Biol Sci. 2008; 4(5): 434-46.
85. Galas E, Kaluzewska M. Proteinases of *Streptomyces fradiae* III Catalytic and some physic-chemical properties of keratinolytic proteinase. Acta Microbiol Pol. 1992; 41:69-71.
86. Moon SH, Parulekar SJ. Parametric study of protein production in batch and fed batch cultures of *Bacillus firmus*. Biotechnol Bioeng. 1991; 37: 467-83.
87. Awad HM, Mostafa EE, Saad MM, Selim MH, Hassan HM. Partial purification and characterization of extracellular protease from a halophilic and thermotolerant strain *Streptomyces pseudogrisiolus* NRC-15. Ind J Biochem Biophysics. 2013; 50: 305-11.
88. Hozzein WN, Li WJ, Ali MIA, Hammouda O, Mousa AS, Xu LH, Jiang CL. *Nocardiopsis alkaliphila* sp. nov., a novel alkaliphilic actinomycete isolated from desert soil in gypt. Int J Syst Evol Microbiol. 2004; 54: 247-52.
89. Mitsui S, Ichikawa M, Oka T, Sakai M, Moriyama Y, Sameshima Y, Goto M, Furukawa K. Molecular characterization of a keratinolytic enzyme from an alkaliphilic *Nocardiopsis* sp. TOA-1. Enzyme Microb Technol. 2004; 34(5): 482-89.
90. Dixit VS, Pant A. Comparative characterization of two serine endopeptidases from *Nocardiopsis* sp. NCIM 5124. Biochim Biophys Acta. 2000; 1523(2-3): 261-68.
91. Jani SA, Chudasama CJ, Purohit AD, Soni PM, Patel HN. Optimization and production of Alkaline and Thermostable protease from thermophilic Actinomycetes SJ-11 Isolated from Aritha (*Apindus laurifolius*), Int J Health Pharm Sci. 2012; 60-69.
92. Gupta R, Beg QK, Khan S, Chauhan B. An overview on fermentation, downstream processing and properties of microbial alkaline proteases. Appl Microbiol Biotechnol. 2002; 60(4): 381-95.
93. Hameed A, Keshavarz T, Evans CS. Effect of dissolved oxygen tension and pH on the production of extracellular protease from a new isolate of *Bacillus subtilis* K2 for use in leather processing. J Chem Technol Biotechnol. 1999; 74: 5-8.
94. Beg QK, Saxena RK, Gupta R. De-repression and subsequent induction of protease synthesis by *Bacillus mojavensis* under fed batch operation. Process Biochem. 2002; 37: 1103-09.
95. Gupta A, Roy I, Patel RK, Singh SP, Khare SK, Gupta MN. One-step purification and characterization of an alkaline protease from haloalkaliphilic *Bacillus* sp. J Chromatogr A. 2005; 1075(1-2): 103-08.
96. Fleming AB, Tangney M, Jorgensen PL, Diderichsen B, Priest FG. Extracellular enzyme synthesis in spore-deficient strain of *Bacillus licheniformis*. Appl Environ Microbiol. 1995; 61: 3775-80.
97. Zamost BL, Brantley QI, Elm DD, Beck CM. Production and characterization of a thermostable protease produced by an asporogenous mutant of *Bacillus stearothermophilus*. J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol. 1990; 5(5): 303-12.
98. Bierbaum G, Giesecke UE, Wandrey C.

- Analysis of nucleotide pools during protease production with *Bacillus licheniformis*. Appl Microbiol Biotechnol. 1991; 35:725-30.
99. Reddy LVA, Wee YJ, Yun JS, Ryu HW. Optimization of alkaline protease production by batch culture of *Bacillus* sp. RKY3 through Plackett-Burman and response surface methodological approaches. Bioresour Technol. 2008; 99: 2242-49.
100. Mukherjee AK, Adhikari H, Rai SK. Production of alkaline protease by a thermophilic *Bacillus subtilis* under solid-state fermentation (SSF) condition using *Imperata cylindrica* grass and potato peel as low-cost medium: Characterization and application of enzyme in detergent formulation. Biochem Eng J. 2008; 39: 353-61.
101. Ibrahim ASS, Al-Salamah AA. Optimisation of media and cultivation conditions for alkaline protease production by alkaliphilic *Bacillus halodurans*. Res J Microbiol. 2009; 4(7): 251-59.
102. Cheng K, Lu FP, Li M, Liu LL, Liang XM. Purification and biochemical characterization of a serine alkaline protease TC4 from a new isolated *Bacillus alcalophilus* TCCC11004 in detergent formulations. Afr J Biotechnol. 2010; 9(31): 4942-53.
103. Joshi GK, Kumar S, Sharma V. Production of moderately halotolerant, SDS stable alkaline protease from *Bacillus cereus* MTCC 6840 isolated from Lake Nainital, Uttarakhand state, India. Braz J Microbiol. 2007; 38: 773-79.
104. Longo MA, Novella IS, Garcia LA, Diaz M. Comparison of *Bacillus subtilis* and *Serratia marcescens* as protease producers under different operating conditions. J Biosci Bioeng. 1999; 88: 35-40.
105. Chen XG, Stabnikova O, Tay JH, Wang JY, Tay STL. Thermo active extracellular proteases of *Geobacillus caldoproteolyticus* sp. from sewage sludge. Extremophiles. 2004; 8: 489-98.
106. Joo HS, Kumar CG, Park GC, Kim GT, Paik SR, Chang CS. Optimization of the production of an extracellular alkaline protease from *Bacillus horikoshii*. Process Biochem. 2002; 38: 155-59.
107. Kumar CG, Tiwari M P and Jany K D (1999) Novel alkaline serine proteases from alkalophilic *Bacillus* sp.: purification and characterization. Process Biochem 34: 441-49.
108. Gessesse A. The use of nug meal as low-cost substrate for the production of alkaline protease by the alkaliphilic *Bacillus* sp. AR-009 and some properties of the enzyme. Bioresour Technol. 1997; 62: 59-61.
109. Mabrouk SS, Hashem AM, El-Shayeb NMA, Ismail AMS, Abdel-Fattah AF. Optimization of alkaline protease productivity by *Bacillus licheniformis* ATCC 21415. Bioresour Technol. 1999; 69: 155-59.
110. Chudasama CJ, Jani SA, Jajda HM, Patel HN. Optimization and production of alkaline protease from *Bacillus thuringiensis* cc7. J Cell Tissue Res. 2010; 10(2): 2257-62.
111. Nadeem M, Qazi JI, Baig S, Syed QUA. Effect of medium composition on commercially important alkaline protease production by *Bacillus licheniformis* N-2. Food Technol Biotechnol. 2008; 46(4): 388-94.
112. He GQ, Chen QH, Zhang L, Liu XJ. Influence of medium components on elastase production using crude sources by *Bacillus* sp. EL31410. J Zhejiang Univ Sci. 2003; 4: 142-51.
113. Shafee N, Aris SN, Rahman RNZA, Basri M, Salleh AB. Optimization of environmental and nutritional conditions for the production of alkaline protease by a newly isolated bacterium *Bacillus cereus* strain 146. J Appl Sci Res. 2005; 1(1): 1-8.
114. Fang YY, Yang WB, Ong SL, Hu JY, Ng WJ. Fermentation of starch for enhanced alkaline protease production by constructing an alkalophilic *Bacillus pumilus* strain. Appl Microbiol Biotechnol. 2001; 57: 153-60.
115. Nilegaonkar SS, Zambare VP, Kanekar PP, Dhakephalkar PK, Sarnaik SS. Production and partial characterization of dehairing protease from *Bacillus cereus* MCM B-326. Bioresour Technol. 2007; 98: 1238-45.
116. Darani KK, Falahatpishe HR, Jalali M. Alkaline protease production on date waste by an alkalophilic *Bacillus* sp. 2-5 isolated from soil. Afr J Biotechnol. 2008; 7(10): 1536-42.
117. Srividya S, Mala M. Influence of process parameters on the production of detergent compatible alkaline protease by a newly isolated *Bacillus* sp. Y. Turk J Biol. 2011; 35: 177-82.
118. Swada J, Yasui H, Amamoto T. Isolation and some properties of anti-polypeptides from potato. Agric Biol Chem. 1974; 38: 59-61.
119. Joo HS, Chang CS. Production of protease from a new alkalophilic *Bacillus* sp. I-312 grown on soybean meal: Optimization and some properties. Process Biochem. 2005; 40:

- 1263-70.
120. Naidu KSB, Devi KL. Optimization of thermostable alkaline protease production from species of *Bacillus* using rice bran. *Afr J Biotechnol.* 2005; 4: 724-26.
121. Ahmed I, Irfan M, Nadeem M, Zia MA, Ahmad BM, Iqbal HMN. Optimization of media and environmental conditions for alkaline protease production using *Bacillus subtilis* in submerged fermentation process. *IJAVMS.* 2010; 4(4):105-13.
122. Kumar PKP, Mathivanan V, Karunakaran M, Renganathan S, Sreenivasan RS. Studies on the effects of pH and incubation period on protease production by *Bacillus* sp. using groundnut cake and wheat bran. *Indian J Sci Technol.* 2008; 1(4): 1-4.
123. Shikha SA, Darmwal NS. Improved production of alkaline protease from a mutant of alkalophilic *Bacillus pantotheneticus* using molasses as a substrate. *Bioresour Technol.* 2006; 98: 881-85.
124. Shampa S, Dasu VV, Bishnupada M. Effect of physical parameters, carbon and nitrogen sources on the production of alkaline protease from a newly isolated *Bacillus pseudofirmus* SVB1. *Ann Microbiol.* 2009; 59(3): 531-38.
125. Jaswal RK, Kocher GS, Virk MS. Production of alkaline protease by *Bacillus circulans* using agricultural residues: A statistical approach. *Ind J Biotechnol.* 2008; 7: 356-60.
126. Kitada M, Horikoshi K. Alkaline protease production from methylacetate by alkalophilic *Bacillus* sp. *J Ferment Technol.* 1976; 54: 383-92.
127. Takii Y, Kuriyama N, Suzuki Y. Alkaline serine protease produced from citric acid by *Bacillus alcalophilus* subsp. *halodurans* KP 1239. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 1990; 34(1): 57-62.
128. Çalik P, Çalik G, Özdamar TH. Oxygen transfer effects in serine alkaline protease fermentation by *Bacillus licheniformis*: Use of citric acid as a carbon sources. *Enzyme Microb Technol.* 1998; 23: 451-61.
129. Stratford M, Lambert RJW. Weak acid preservatives: Mechanism of adaptation and resistance by yeast. *Food Australia.* 1999; 51: 26-29.
130. Prakasham RS, Rao CS, Sarma PN. Green gram husk-an inexpensive substrate for alkaline protease production by *Bacillus* sp. in solid-state fermentation. *Bioresour Technol.* 2006; 97: 1449-54.
131. Ferrero MA, Castro GR, Abate CM, Biagori MD, Sineriz F. Thermostable alkaline protease of *Bacillus licheniformis* MIR 29: Isolation, production and characterization. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 1996; 45: 327-32.
132. Kaur M, Dhillon S, Chaudhary K. Production, purification and characterization of a thermostable alkaline protease from *Bacillus polymyxa*. *Indian J Microbiol.* 1998; 38: 63-67.
133. Nilegaonkar SS, Kanekar PP, Sarnaik SS, Kelkar MS. Production, isolation and characterization of extracellular protease of an alkaliphilic strain of *Arthrobacter ramosus*, MCM B-351 isolated from an alkaline lake of Lonar, India. *World J Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2002; 18: 785-89.
134. Chu IM, Lee C, Li TS. Production and degradation of alkaline protease in batch cultures of *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 14416. *Enzyme Microb Technol.* 1992; 14: 755-61.
135. Kaur S, Vohra RM, Kapoor M, Beg QK, Hoondal GS. Enhanced production and characterization of a highly thermostable alkaline protease from *Bacillus* sp. P-2. *World J Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2001; 17: 125-29.
136. Fakhfakh N, Kanoun S, Manni L, Nasri M. Production and biochemical and molecular characterization of a keratinolytic serine protease from chicken feather-degrading *Bacillus licheniformis* RPK. *Can J Microbiol.* 2009; 55: 427-36.
137. Abdel-Raof UM. Studies of proteolytic bacteria isolated from certain localities in Aswan city. M.Sc. thesis. Al Azhar University, Asuit, Egypt. 1991.
138. Rao K, Narasu ML. Alkaline protease from *Bacillus firmus* 7728. *Afr J Biotechnol.* 2007; 6(21): 2493-96.
139. Saurabh S, Jasmine I, Pritesh G, Rajendra KS. Enhanced productivity of serine alkaline protease by *Bacillus* sp. using soybean as substrate. *Mal J Microbiol.* 2007; 3(1): 1-6.
140. Kanekar PP, Nilegaonkar SS, Sarnaik SS. Optimization of protease activity of alkaliphilic bacteria isolated from an alkaline lake in India. *Bioresour Technol.* 2002; 85(1): 87-93.
141. Kanchana M, Padmavathy S. Optimization of extracellular alkaline protease enzyme from *Bacillus* Sp. *Bioscan.* 2010; 5(1): 85-87.
142. Sen S, Satyanarayana T. Optimization of alkaline protease production by thermophilic *Bacillus licheniformis* S-40. *Ind J Microbiol.* 1993; 33: 43-47.

143. Deshpande VV, Laxman RS, More SV, Rele MV, Rao BSR, Jogdand VV, Rao MB, Naidu RB, Maniknandan P, Kumar DA, Kanagaraj J, Samayavaram R, Samivelu N, Rengarajulu P. Process for preparation of an alkaline protease. 2004; U.S. Patent, 6777219.
144. Çalik P, Çelik E, Telli IE, Oktar C, Özdemir E. Protein-based complex medium design for recombinant serine alkaline protease production. *Enzyme Microb Technol.* 2003; 33: 975-86.
145. Shaheen M, Ali Shah A, Hameed A, Hasan F. Influence of culture conditions on production and activity of protease from *Bacillus Subtilis* BS1. *Pak J Bot.* 2008; 40(5): 2161-69.
146. Joo HS, Chang CS. Oxidant and SDS-stable alkaline protease from a halo-tolerant *Bacillus clausii* I-52: enhanced production and simple purification. *J Appl Microbiol.* 2005; 98(2): 491-97.
147. El Hadj-Ali N, Hmidet N, Souissi N, Sellami-Kamoun A, Nasri M. The use of an economical medium for the production of alkaline serine proteases by *Bacillus licheniformis* NH1. *Afr J Biotechnol.* 2010; 9(18): 2668-74.
148. Chu WH. Optimization of extracellular alkaline protease production from species of *Bacillus*. *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2007; 34(3): 241-45.
149. Uyar F, Baysal Z. Production and optimization of process parameters for alkaline protease production by newly isolated *Bacillus* sp. under solid state fermentation process. *Biochem.* 2004; 39: 1893-98.
150. Nascimento RP, Avila-levy CM, Souza RF, Branquinha MH, Bon EPS. Production and partial characterization of extracellular proteinases from *Streptomyces malaysiensis* isolated from a Brazilian cerrado soil. *Arch Microbiol.* 2005; 184: 194-98.
151. Abdel-Naby MA, Ismail AMS, Ahmed SA, Abdel-Fattah AF. Production and immobilization of alkaline protease from *Bacillus mycoides*. *Bioresour Technol.* 1998; 64:205-10.
152. Mehrotra S, Pandey PK, Gaur R, Darmwal NS. The production of alkaline protease by a *Bacillus* species isolate. *Bioresour Technol.* 1999; 67: 201-03.
153. Kumar CG. Purification and characterization of a thermostable alkaline protease from alkalophilic *Bacillus pumilus*. *Lett Appl Microbiol.* 2002; 34(1): 13-17.
154. Adinarayana K, Ellaiah P, Prasad DS. Purification and partial characterization of thermostable serine alkaline protease from a newly isolated *Bacillus subtilis* PE-11. *AAPS Pharm Sci Tech.* 2003; 4(4) Article 56:1-9.
155. Beg QK, Sahai V, Gupta R. Statistical media optimization and alkaline protease production from *Bacillus mojavensis* in a bioreactor. *Process Biochem.* 2003; 39: 203-09.
156. Chauhan B, Gupta R. Application of statistical experimental design for optimization of alkaline protease production from *Bacillus* sp. RGR-14. *Process Biochem.* 2004; 39(12): 2115-22.
157. Joshi GK, Kumar S, Sharma V. Production of moderately halotolerant, SDS stable alkaline protease from *Bacillus cereus* MTCC 6840 isolated from Lake Nainital, Uttaranchal state, India. *Braz J Microbiol.* 2007; 38: 773-79.
158. Balaji S, Kumar MS, Karthikeyan R, Kumar R, Kirubanandan S, Sridhar R, Sehgal PK. Purification and characterization of an extracellular keratinase from a hornmeal-degrading *Bacillus subtilis* MTCC 9102. *World J Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2008; 24: 2741-45.
159. Akcan N. Production of extracellular protease in submerged fermentation by *Bacillus licheniformis* ATCC 12759. *Afr J Biotechnol.* 2012; 11(7): 1729-35.
160. Asokan S, Jayanthi C. Alkaline protease production by *Bacillus licheniformis* and *Bacillus coagulans*. *J Cell Tiss Res.* 2010; 10: 2119-23.
161. Shrinivas D, Naik GR. (2011) Characterization of alkaline thermostable keratinolytic protease from thermoalkaliphilic *Bacillus halodurans* JB 99 exhibiting dehairing activity. *Int Biodeter Biodegrad.* 2011; 65: 29-35.
162. Shimizu Y, Nishino T, Murad S. Purification and characterization of a membrane bound serine protease of *Bacillus subtilis*. IFO 3027. *Agric Biol Chem.* 1983; 47: 1775-82.
163. Okada J, Shimogaki H, Murata K, Kimura A. Cloning of the gene responsible for the extracellular proteolytic activities of *Bacillus licheniformis*. *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol.* 1984; 20: 21-25.
164. Durham DR, Stewart DB, Stellwag EJ. Novel alkaline and heat stable serine proteases from alkalophilic *Bacillus* sp. strain GX6638. *Bacteriol.* 1987; 169(6): 2762-68.
165. Fujiwara N, Masui A, Imanaka T. Purification and properties of the highly thermostable

- alkaline protease from an alkaliphilic and thermophilic *Bacillus* sp. *Biotechnol.* 1993; 30(2): 245-56.
166. Mane RR, Bapat M. A study of extracellular alkaline protease from *Bacillus subtilis* NCIM 2713. *Indian J Exp Biol.* 2001; 39(6): 578-83.
167. Tang XM, Wang ZX, Shao WL, Liu JQ, Fang HY, Zhang J. Study on fermentation condition of alkaline protease gene engineering strain and the purification and characterization of recombinant enzyme. *Sheng Wu Gong Cheng Xue Bao.* 2002; 18(6): 729-34.
168. Prakash M, Banik RM, Koch-Brandt C. Purification and characterization of *Bacillus cereus* protease suitable for detergent industry. *Appl Biochem Biotechnol.* 2005; 127(3): 143-55.
169. Kazan D, Denizci AA, Oner MN, Erarslan A. Purification and characterization of a serine alkaline protease from *Bacillus clausii* GMBAE 42. *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol.* 2005; 32(8): 335-44.
170. Guangrong H, Tiejing Y, Po H, Jiaying J. Purification and characterization of a protease from thermophilic *Bacillus* strain HS08. *Afr J Biotechnol.* 2006; 5(24): 2433-38.
171. Banik RM, Prakash M. Purification and characterization of laundry detergent compatible alkaline protease from *Bacillus cereus*. *Ind J Biotechnol.* 2006; 5: 380-84.
172. Hezayen FF, Younis MAM, Nour-Eldein MA, Shabeb MSA. Optimization of purified protease produced in low-cost medium by *Bacillus subtilis* KO strain. *World Appl Sci J.* 2009; 7(4): 453-60.
173. Jaswal RK, Kocher GS. Partial characterization of a crude alkaline protease from *Bacillus circulans* and its detergent compatibility. *Internet J Microbiol.* 2007; 4: 1.
174. Towatana NH, Painupong A, Suntinanaler P. Purification and characterization of an extracellular protease from alkaliphilic and thermophilic *Bacillus* sp. PS719. *J Biosci Bioeng.* 1999; 87: 581-87.
175. Kato T, Yamagata Y, Arai T, Ichishima E. Purification of new extracellular 90 kDa serine proteinase with isoelectric point of 3.9 from *Bacillus subtilis* (natto) and elucidation of its distinct mode of action. *Biosci Biotech Biochem.* 1992; 56: 1166-68.
176. Jellouli K, Bellaaj OG, Ayed HB, Manni L, Agrebi R, Nasri M. Alkaline-protease from *Bacillus licheniformis* MP1: Purification, characterization and potential application as a detergent additive and for shrimp waste deproteinization. *Process Biochem.* 2011; 46: 1248-56.
177. Ahmed I, Zia MA, Iqbal HMN. Purification and kinetic parameters characterization of an alkaline protease produced from *Bacillus subtilis* through submerged fermentation technique. *World Appl Sci J.* 2011; 12(6): 751-57.
178. Ravindran B, Ganesh Kumar A, Aruna Bhavani PS, Sekaran G. Solid-state fermentation for the production of alkaline protease by *Bacillus cereus* 1173900 using proteinaceous tannery solid waste. *Curr Sci.* 2011; 100(5): 726-30.
179. Nam MS, Whang KS, Choi SH, Bae HC, Kim YK, Park YW. Purification, characterization, and properties of an alkaline protease produced by *Serratia marcescens* S3-R1 inhabiting Korean ginseng rhizosphere. *J Sci Food Agr.* 2013; 93(15): 3876-82.
180. Asker MMS, Mahmoud MG, El-Shebwy K, Abd el Aziz MS. Purification and characterization of two thermostable protease fractions from *Bacillus megaterium*. *J Genetic Eng Biotechnol.* 2013; 11(2): 103-09.
181. Roostita LB, Putranto WS, Charoenchai C, Wulandari E, Gemilang LU. Purification Crude Extracellular Protease of *Saccharomycopsis fibuligera* strain R64 Isolated from *Tape* Indonesian Fermented Food. *Adv J Food Sci Technol.* 2013; 5(8):1002-04.
182. Liu Q, Sun S, Piao M, Yang JY. Purification and Characterization of a Protease Produced by *Planomicrobium* sp. L-2 from Gut of *Octopus vulgaris*. *Prev Nutr Food Sci.* 2013; 18(4): 273-79.
183. Iqbal I, Aftab MN, Afzal M, Ur-Rehman A, Aftab S, Zafar A, Ud-Din Z, Khuharo AR, Iqbal J, Ul-Haq I. Purification and characterization of cloned alkaline protease gene of *Geobacillus stearothermophilus*. *J Basic Microbiol.* 2015; 55(2): 160-71.
184. Chaplin MF, Bucke C. The large-scale use of enzymes in solution. In: Chaplin M F and Bucke C (ed) *Enzyme Technology*. U K Cambridge University Press, London. 1990; Pp 138-66.
185. Banerjee UC, Sani RK, Azmi W, Soni R. Thermostable alkaline protease from *Bacillus brevis* and its characterization as a laundry detergent additive. *Process Biochem.* 1999; 35: 213-19.
186. Margesin R, Palma N, Knauseder F, Schinner

- F. Purification and characterization of an alkaline serine protease produced by a psychrotrophic *Bacillus* sp. J Biotechnol. 1992; 24: 203-06.
187. Potumarthi R, Subhakar C, Jetty A. Alkaline protease production by submerged fermentation in stirred tank reactor using *Bacillus licheniformis* NCIM-2042: Effect of aeration and agitation regimes. Biochem Eng J. 2007; 34: 185-92.
188. Ozturk B. Immobilization of lipase from *Candida rugosa* on hydrophobic and hydrophilic supports. 2001; M.Sc. Thesis, İzmir Institute of Technology, Biotechnology Department, Izmir.
189. Rao MB, Tanksale AM, Ghatge MS, Deshpande VV. Molecular and biotechnological aspects of microbial proteases. Microbiol Mole Biol Rev. 1998; 62(3): 597-635.
190. Haki GD, Rakshit SK. Developments in industrially important thermostable enzymes: a review. Bioresour Technol. 2003; 89: 17-34.
191. Matta H, Punj V. Isolation and partial characterization of a thermostable extracellular protease of *Bacillus polymyxa* B-17. Int J Food Microbiol. 1998; 42: 139-45.
192. Huang Q, Peng Y, Li X, Wang HF, Zhang YZ. Purification and characterization of an extracellular alkaline serine protease with dehairing function from *Bacillus pumilus*. Curr Microbiol. 2003; 46(3): 169-73.
193. Arulmani M, Aparanjini K, Vasanthi K, Arumugam P, Arivuchelvi M, Kalaichelvan PT. Purification and partial characterization of serine protease from thermostable alkalophilic *Bacillus laterosporus*-AK1. World J Microbiol Biotechnol. 2007; 23: 475-81.
194. Hirata Y, Ito H, Furuta T, Ikuta K, Sakudo A. Degradation and destabilization of abnormal prion protein using alkaline detergents and proteases. Int J Mol Med. 2010; 25: 267-70.
195. Rao CH, Sathish T, Ravichandra P, Prakasham RS. Characterization of thermo and detergent stable serine protease from isolated *Bacillus circulans* and evaluation of eco-friendly applications. Process Biochem. 2009; 44: 262-68.
196. Sinha N, Satyanarayana T. Alkaline protease production by thermophilic *Bacillus licheniformis*. Indian J Microbiol. 1991; 31(4): 425-30.
197. Singh S, Gaur R, Agarwal SK, Darmwal NS. Partitioning and properties of alkaline protease from *Bacillus* in aqueous biphasic system. Indian J Microbiol. 2002; 42: 343-45.
198. Kumar CG, Joo HS, Koo YM, Palik SR, Chang CS. Thermostable alkaline protease from a novel marine haloalkalophilic *Bacillus clausii* isolate. World J Microbiol Biotechnol. 2004; 20(4): 351-57.
199. Ul-Haq I, Mukhtar H. Fuzzy logic control of bioreactor for enhanced biosynthesis of alkaline protease by an alkalophilic strain of *Bacillus subtilis*. Curr Microbiol. 2006; 52(2): 149-52.
200. Jang J, Ko J, Kim E, Jang W, Kang J, Yoo O. Enhanced thermal stability of an alkaline protease, AprP, isolated from a *Pseudomonas* sp. by mutation at an autoproteolysis site, Ser-331. Biotechnol App Biochem. 2001; 34: 81-84.
201. Irfan M, Nadeem M, Syed Q, Nawaz W, Baig S, Qureshi AM. Relationship of Process Parameters for the Production of Alkaline Protease by *Bacillus* sp. Int J Agro Vet Med Sci. 2010; 4(4): 114-20.
202. Zambare VP, Nilegaonkar SS, Kanekar PP. Production of an alkaline protease by *Bacillus cereus* MCM B-326 and its application as a dehairing agent. World J Microbiol Biotechnol. 2007; 23: 1569-74.